

GYMNASTICS IS THE MAIN FORM OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSON

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Abstract. Education and training of young students is carried out in the course of educational work in class and extracurricular activities, as well as in socially useful work. Gymnastics is given great attention in the national programs of personnel training in the rules of secondary general education and higher education, as well as in new forms of education.

Keywords. Physical education, student youth, groups, gymnastics.

Introduction. As President Shavkat Miramonovich Mirziyaev said, "the new model of education leads to the formation of a free person who thinks independently in society. We will have the opportunity to educate young people who have a strong will, full of faith and a clear purpose in life, who realize their value. After that, conscious marriage becomes the main criterion of society's life.

This instruction fully applies to the work of physical education of students studying in higher educational institutions. Physical education classes are such a form that they cover all students. Classes are held with the composition of groups from these faculties. This allows for better organization and conduct of training, taking into account specific conditions and training of participants. Physical

education classes are held according to a fixed schedule, on a certain day of the week, for 45 or 90 minutes during a certain period of time.

Proper training ensures that the student correctly performs various exercises related to improving the success of independent work. Students do these exercises independently at home or in groups. Lessons are the basis of students' independent or group activities.

In the classes, which are usually held in the student's dormitories or before practice time, gymnastics, recess and physical education minutes are introduced to the materials used. From the teacher's short conversations during the lesson, students will have clear information about the importance of physical education exercises and their need for health.

Students feel that physical education has a great practical value only when they master the methods of performing human organs (subjects and without objects) while learning independent exercises.

Among the physical exercises used in physical education classes, there are many vital exercises that can be applied in everyday life. The purpose of these exercises is to accustom students to use physical education tools every day in various conditions of learning, work, and recreation. Young people learn all this first in physical education classes.

Physical education classes have their own characteristics according to their content and organization. They are held at home in the hall, on the field, in such places the movement of young people is less restricted, which creates special conditions for performing exercises and conducting training.

Physical education exercises are distinguished by a large number of very diverse movement sensations that affect the body. An individual approach is necessary to master the exercises well.

All of these characteristics increase the responsibilities of youth physical education.

Requirements for the lesson when performing the exercises.

-Each physical education exercise should serve as the main tool in solving the tasks assigned to the lesson.

- A complex of exercises for solving certain general and specific tasks, general tasks are included in the exercises performed during all lessons or a series of lessons, and specific tasks are included in exercises performed during a separate lesson.

- Exercises should be methodically structured correctly.

- To compile a complex of morning gymnastics exercises, physical training minute exercises in terms and pictorial records and to teach it in different ways.

- Creation of exercises affecting all parts of the body, which help in all-round physical development, strengthening of health, formation of stature.

- Correct use of the medical gymnastics exercise complex and methods of its execution.

Requirements for the volume of practical exercises to be performed by young people.

- Regular assimilation of exercises to the student's training sessions.

- To study the professional skills of determining the working capacity and physical fitness of the organism.

- Fulfilling the personal and normative requirements of the studied physical exercise methods.

- proper use of gymnastic equipment and equipment.

Use of new technologies in teaching exercises. Educational technologies can be used in learning exercises. In this case, it is appropriate to use theoretical and methodological-descriptive notes on the development of physical training exercises through diagrams, multimedia, pictures and the necessary new literature, improving the structure of the body, and developing physical indicators of therapeutic gymnastics applied to various diseases that shape the figure.

Tasks of physical education exercises. The results of the exercise process in physical education depend on the quality of the educational and educational work carried out in the training. In this case, each lesson can be achieved only by consistently solving the tasks. Physical education exercises are divided into 3 types:

1) Educational tasks

2) Educational tasks

3) Health is divided into tasks.

Education: Teaching tasks are to teach students to perform the exercises provided in the program, to improve the learned exercises, as well as to develop skills and abilities, to apply the learned exercises in different conditions.

Consistent completion of educational tasks leads to systematic and solid learning of the entire educational material in the program. A relatively long time is needed to solve some educational tasks, and one lesson is enough to solve some of them.

The implementation of educational tasks is usually carried out with the tasks of upbringing and health.

Educational tasks. Attention, discipline, will, organization, care of things, as well as friendship, camaraderie, striving for a goal, independence and persistence in overcoming difficulties are cultivated. Cultivating the qualities of perseverance and bravery is carried out by using exercises (jumping, balancing, running) that require the same qualities to be demonstrated in training. Gymnastic exercises are voluntary movements controlled by the mind. In the formation of movement skills, the performance of movements increases to the level of automation. This is not to say that there is no conscious movement, because bringing the movement to the level of automation requires conscious learning of physical exercises. Teachers and coaches monitor, evaluate and correct mistakes. Nevertheless, it is important to develop the ability of the participants to evaluate and control their own actions. In this, the methods of pre-sensing and testing movements are often used. After the learned gymnastic exercise techniques and skills are formed, they are taught a series of more complex physical exercises. Easy exercises reduce student activity. Therefore, it is necessary to give them physical exercises according to their physical level and improve them. Students' bodies adapt to the same form of exercise. Increasing the amount, volume, and form of exercises ensures the physical development of the children's body. Otherwise, the body of students will adapt to the same form of exercise and their organism will not develop physically. The principle of performance and individualization means taking into account the characteristics of the students and how difficult or easy the task is

given to them. It means that the process of education and training in physical education should be organized taking into account the capabilities of the participants, age and gender characteristics, level of preparation, as well as individual differences in physical and spiritual abilities. The ability to perform gymnastic exercises, on the one hand, depends on the capabilities of the participants, and on the other hand, it depends on the objective difficulties that occur during the performance of an exercise. When the teacher sets the standard of performance, it is first based on the programs and normative requirements determined for a certain contingent of students on the basis of scientific information and generalized practical experiences. The capabilities of the employees are determined by physical fitness tests, medical supervision and pedagogical observations.

The principle of performance can be understood as defining the standard of physical actions that can be performed with the help of the physical and spiritual forces of the participants. Also, if vigorous forms of exercise are considered beyond the capacity of the exerciser, it becomes an impossible load. In the following periods, such loadings can also be calculated from the opportunity of those involved. If gymnastic loads provide physical development and health in the body, they are loads that can be performed. Physical loads that have a negative effect on the body and harm health are considered impossible loads. Nevertheless, with the development of the athlete's body, the level of loads that cannot be performed decreases. Attempting to carry out a feasible load should also be under the supervision of a pedagogue and a doctor, because they give instructions to eliminate the negative effects of loads on the body. In addition to the conditions specified at each stage of physical education, the standard of performance is determined by the appropriateness of the chosen method and the organization of the training as a whole. Competences and skills are a base of previously acquired

skills. Therefore, the issue of ability to perform is inextricably linked with other methods of education and training, with the methods of regularly increasing the duration of training and difficulties. One of the decisive conditions for performance in the process of physical education is the duration of the gymnastic exercise. Continuity is achieved from the natural interrelationships between different forms of movement and structurally. Training should be organized in such a way that the learned movement tasks provide easy mastering of future training tasks.

This pattern is called transition from known to unknown or mastered to unmastered task. One of the most important conditions in moving from one task to another, from easy to difficult, is consistency. The benefits of regular exercise are immeasurable. The regularity of the physical education process is mainly a feature of how much it depends on the most convenient sequence of loading and rest. Continuity - physical education is a continuous process from all periods of human life. the functional and structural changes occurring in the body due to gymnastic exercises come into conflict, the conditioned reflex connection begins to fade, the achieved level of functional capabilities decreases, and even some regressive changes become apparent after 5-7 days of non-exercise. It is clear that the process of physical education should be continuous, that is, unnecessary breaks should be eliminated, and only after that, the conditions for achieving physical maturity will be created. Repetition and renewal of exercises In the process of physical education, more space is given to repetition than in most other types of education. In addition to repetition for the process of physical education, it is also important to vary, that is, to frequently change the conditions of gymnastic exercises and their performance, to gradually increase loads and to apply various methods of their use, and to change the form and content of training in general. Loading is a factor of the level of influence of gymnastics exercises on

the body and the development of the body's functional capabilities. In recovery, as a consequence and effect of loading, rest is inextricably linked with loading. Taking into account the organic connection and coexistence of fatigue and recovery processes, it is possible to understand the interdependence of loading and rest. The results of scientific studies show that a person's ability to work varies during work and rest.

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